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Oncogene expression results in activation of ETS transcription factor expression, including ETV4.

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We describe here induction of the transcription factors of the ETS family resulting from expression of oncogenic KRas G12D and KRas G12V, including ETV4. We recently demonstrated induction of homeoboxes transcription factors by oncogene expression, and their control of KRas. Oncogenes, homeoboxes, and transcription factors like those of the ETS family likely function in a tightly co-regulated network in transformation and transformation control.

Results

Figure 1: Expression of KRas G12D in human cells results in induction of ETV4.

GSE239737

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
2118	2.19E-168	0.1797	-2.77E+01	-4.97	453.83	ETV4	643/16752	96.1

Figure 2: Trametinib silences activation of ETV4 by KRas G12D.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
2118	7.17E-03	0.3154	-2.688985	-0.8480682	40.72	ETV4	11604/16752	30.7

Figure 3: Induction of TNFSF4 by Kras G12D in the presence of trametinib is intact.

3b. Induction of TNFSF4 by Kras G12D.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7292	0	0.1	-4.40E+01	-4.4	1529.36	TNFSF4	22/16752	99.9

3b. Induction of TNFSF4 by KRas G12D + trametinib.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7292	0	0.0907	-54.609874	-4.9517744	2290.88	TNFSF4	20/17078	99.9

Figure 4: Induction of ETV4 by a second KRas mutant, KRas G12V.

GSE146479

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
2118	8.64E-02	0.164	-1.714946	-0.2811753	7997.5	ETV4	5349/19959	73.2

The data demonstrated that ETV4 activation by oncogenic KRas was specific.

Figure 5: Wild-type KRas does not activate ETV4; rather, ETV4 is silenced by wild-type KRas.

GSE146479

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
2118	1.47E-06	0.1274	4.8158272	0.6136041	5269.86	ETV4	1647/19751	91.7

Discussion

We described here a biological phenomenon wherein cells respond to KRas mutant oncogene expression by activation expression of the transcription factor ETV4. Oncogenes, homeoboxes, and transcription factors like those of the ETS family likely function in a tightly co-regulated network in transformation and transformation control.